

Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding

Live Performances (including audio, visual, and A/V or multimedia) will largely be sorted into one of two formats: a concert format, with seated audience; and an Algorave format, unseated and intended for dancing.

1. General Information

- **Performance Title:** Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding
- **Performers:** Dahee Park
- **Main Contact:** daheepvrk@gmail.com
- **Performance Type:** Concert

2. Abstract

<Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding> is a live coding project by Dahee Park. In this project, she explores how to play the computer through live coding. Each of the three pieces in the project, as the title suggests, attempts to modify a repetitive pattern and encounter coincidences in the process. There's a principle to the project, and that is to start writing all the pieces from scratch (except for the basic setup). She also pays attention to the "temporality" of the performance, in which the codes entered are not only spelled correctly, but also the speed at which the performer types them and the timing of their execution. At the end of each piece, the code written by the artist is documented and made public, like a musical score.

<Performance List>

-Pattern 1

-Noise for Sound Sculpture

-Repetition and Coincidence

3. Video Material

<Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding>

[LINK](#)

4. Program Note

<Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding> is a live coding project by electronic music artist Dahee Park, where at the end of each piece, the artist's code is documented and made public, like a musical score.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Dahee Park is an electronic musician based in South Korea. She is active in the field of live recording and live performance with modular synthesizers. She enjoys working with limited environments and mediums. Since 2021, Park has performed at electronic music festivals such as WeSA Festival and GIGANOISE Tokyo, and in 2023, she released her first album, <Mangled>. She also held her solo debut performance, <Repetition, Coincidence, Computer! Live Coding>, and has taught various sound + technology workshops such as <Live API with Max for Live>, <Max RNBO with Raspberry Pi>, and <Mangled Sound>.


```
~"
d 8 7 (linger(1/"32 64") . scramble 4)
16 (fast 2 . mask "t ~ t t ~")
[
k $ n "2!16" # gain "1 0.5 0.7"
rum

k [
  p_synth
27 # sustain1
segment "16"
ge 0 127 $ rand) # lpf1
27 # feedback1
27 # lpq1

="{0 ~ ~ 0 0 0 ~ ~ ~ [0 ~ ~ 0]}%8"
"4 8"
y 8 (fast 2 . trunc 0.25)
y' 16 1 (fast 2)
k [
pattern1.tidal [+]
```

```
919 ] # drum
920 :}
921 tidal> :{
922 do
923 let pat1 = "{0@3 0 0 1@5 [ 1 3 ] 2!4}%16"
924 d1
925 $ mask "t ~!4"
926 $ whenmod 8 7 (linger(1/"32 64") . scramble 4)
927 $ every 16 (fast 2 . mask "t ~ t t ~")
928 $ stack [
929   n pat1
930   , brak $ n "2!16" # gain "1 0.5 0.7"
931   ] # drum
932 :}
933 tidal> :{
934 do
935 let pat1 = "{0@3 0 0 1@5 [ 1 3 ] 2!4}%16"
936 d1
937 $ mask "~"
938 $ whenmod 8 7 (linger(1/"32 64") . scramble 4)
939 $ every 16 (fast 2 . mask "t ~ t t ~")
940 $ stack [
941   n pat1
942   , brak $ n "2!16" # gain "1 0.5 0.7"
943   ] # drum
944 :}
945 tidal
```

57,3

